

Full-Length Article

Effects of different concentrations of a white grape marc extract on broiler performance, apparent ileal digestibility, antioxidant capacity, intestinal barrier function and nutrient transport markers

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ABSTRACT

The current study evaluated the effect of a white grape marc extract (GME) on growth performance, gut health, and intestinal function in broiler chickens at different dosages to determine a dose-related efficacy of the extract without inducing any adverse effects. Four hundred male broiler chickens received a basal diet without (CON) or with the GME at different levels, based on its polyphenolic concentration: 200 (LPP), 750 (MPP), and 1,500 (HPP) mg/kg, respectively. Growth performance parameters were recorded during the whole trial. At 35 days, apparent ileal digestibility (AID) of several nutrients was determined. Additionally, jejunal and cecal tissues were collected to assess tissue morphology. Jejunal tissue was also gathered for gene expression and Ussing chamber studies. Finally, breast muscle was collected for lipid oxidation assessment. Dietary supplementation of the GME did not significantly impact the growth performance of broiler chickens with the exception of the FCR that seemed to be increased by the GME supplementation ($P = 0.083$). The AID of most of the analyzed nutrients was also unaffected with the exception of the amino acid aspartic acid, which was higher in MPP and HPP compared to LPP ($P = 0.006$). No significant differences ($P > 0.05$) were found in villus length (VL), crypt depth (CD), villus-to-crypt ratio (V/C) in the jejunum, or in cecal CD. The number of goblet cells in jejunal villi and crypts was higher in MPP and HPP than in CON ($P < 0.001$). There were no effects on the mRNA abundance of some pro-inflammatory cytokines, mucins, or tight junction proteins measured in jejunal tissue nor on antioxidant capacity measured in breast muscle. In the Ussing chamber experiment, the GME decreased jejunal tissue conductance after glucose addition in MPP and HPP groups ($P = 0.033$). In conclusion, although the inclusion of a white GME in the diet of broiler chickens did not significantly enhance growth performance or nutrient absorption, it was confirmed that none of the tested concentrations induced adverse effects.

Introduction

Enhancing poultry performance and maintaining animal welfare and health are primary objectives for sustainable poultry production (Korver, 2023). Traditionally, antibiotic growth promoters have been incorporated into poultry feed to achieve these goals; however, the widespread use of antibiotics has resulted in the emergence of antibiotic-resistant pathogens, posing significant health risks to both humans and animals (Roth et al., 2019). In response to this One Health issue, the European Union implemented a ban on the addition of

antibiotic growth promoters to animal feed (Regulation 1831/2003/EC). This regulatory shift accelerated the exploration of alternative, plant-based solutions for maintaining poultry health and performance (Viveros et al., 2011).

White grape marc, a by-product of grape processing, is rich in bioactive compounds (Chedea et al., 2018). The composition of white grape marc includes a rich mixture of polyphenols, dietary fibers, and essential nutrients (Rama et al., 2021). Polyphenols are one of the most significant components, responsible for many of the bioactive properties (Luca et al., 2020; Rama et al., 2021). These include flavonoids such as

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catechins or quercetin, which are known for their potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects (Cao et al., 2015; Luca et al., 2020). Additionally, phenolic acids like gallic acid and caffeic acid contribute to antimicrobial and antioxidant benefits (Lima et al., 2016). Flavonoids in white grape marc enhance the antioxidant capacity of the marc, helping to neutralize free radicals and reduce oxidative stress (Cantos et al., 2002; Georgiev et al., 2014). Key flavonoids present in the marc include catechin, epicatechin, and quercetin (Georgiev et al., 2014). The dietary fiber content in white grape marc supports digestive health by promoting regular bowel movements and acting as a prebiotic to nourish beneficial gut bacteria (Perra et al., 2022; Abreu et al., 2024). Organic acids such as tartaric acid, malic acid, and citric acid help preserve the marc and add to its overall health effects (Chen et al., 2023). Tannins, another type of polyphenols found in grape marc, possess astringent properties and contribute to its antimicrobial activity (Scalbert, 1991; Huang et al., 2018; Fraga-Corral et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023). Finally, aromatic compounds in white grape marc contribute to its flavor and aroma (Benkwitz et al., 2012; Jelley et al., 2020).

Dietary polyphenol-rich grape products can affect not only intestinal microbiota but also gut morphology in broiler chicks (Viveros et al., 2011; Gungor et al., 2021). The molecular pathways behind the effects of dietary polyphenols on gut microbiota and intestinal permeability highlight the potential of these compounds to improve barrier function and overall gut health (Kasprzak-Drozd et al., 2021; Cheng et al., 2023). Thus, polyphenols may interact with mucin to reinforce intestinal mucus barrier properties, enhancing gut health (Feng et al., 2022).

The use of white grape extracts, particularly polyphenols, as feed additives offers a natural and cost-effective means to enhance poultry health. This study focused on the application of a solid white grape marc extract (GME) as a feed additive for broiler chickens. The primary objectives were to evaluate its effects on growth performance, apparent ileal digestibility, antioxidant capacity, and expressions of different markers of intestinal physiology. Specifically, the study aimed to determine the dose-related efficacy of the solid white GME that could provide the most significant benefits without adverse effects.

Material and methods

Animals and housing

Procedures involving animal handling and treatment were approved by the State Office of Health and Social Affairs Berlin (LAGeSo Reg. No. 0439/17).

A total of 400 healthy, 1-day-old male Cobb 500 broiler chickens were sexed and vaccinated against Infectious Bronchitis (IB Primer: Zoetis) and Newcastle Disease (ND: Merial AviNew) at the hatchery. The birds were randomly allocated by body weight (BW) into 40 pens, each bedded with Giant Miscanthus grass, chopped into one-inch pieces. The pens measured approximately 1.7 × 1.9 m, providing an average space of 0.32 square meters per bird.

Feeders were monitored daily and adjusted as necessary to ensure that approximately 50 % of the bottom of the feed trough remained visible, minimizing feed spillage. Any spoiled or wet feed was removed daily, collected in buckets, weighed, freeze-dried, and the amounts were used to correct feed intake data. Drinkers were also checked daily to ensure consistent water flow.

During the 35-day feeding period, the poultry house was maintained with controlled temperature, relative humidity, lighting, and forced ventilation. Airflow was set at 0.3 m/s from day 1 to day 18, increasing to 0.7 m/s from day 19 onwards. The room temperature was gradually decreased from approximately 33 °C on day 1 to 22 °C by day 28. Relative humidity was maintained between 50 % and 60 %. Environmental parameters were regularly monitored and adjusted as needed to maintain conditions within the targeted range.

Experimental Design and Dietary Treatments

The experiment was structured into four treatment groups, each comprising 10 replicate pens with 10 broiler chickens per pen. The treatments involved varying concentrations of a solid white GME, based on its polyphenolic concentration: the control group (CON) received no extract, while the treatment groups LPP, MPP, and HPP were supplemented with low (200 mg/kg), medium (750 mg/kg), and high concentrations (1,500 mg/kg) of polyphenols coming from the GME, respectively. The Total Polyphenolic Content (TPC) of the extract was 35 g polyphenols/kg GME. This concentration was taken into account to determine the necessary amount of extract to be added to the feed. The individual polyphenolic composition of the extract is shown in Suppl. Table 1. The GME was initially obtained in liquid form, and maltodextrin was used as a carrier for its dry form, which was the one added to the feed. Thus, maltodextrin was added to all the diets to ensure the same amount of this component in all of them.

Over the 35-day experimental period, two basal diets were administered: a mash diet from days 0 to 10 (Table 1), followed by a pelleted

Table 1

Composition of the starter diets for broiler chickens (0 to 10 days) with varying polyphenol levels.

		CON ¹	LPP	MPP	HPP
Ingredient composition					
Maize	g/kg	354	354	354	354
Soybean meal	g/kg	334	334	334	334
Wheat	g/kg	179	176	175	170
Soybean oil	g/kg	58.4	58.2	56.0	54.0
Limestone	g/kg	15.1	15.1	15.0	15.0
Monocalcium - phosphate	g/kg	14.8	14.8	15.0	15.0
Premix ²	g/kg	12.0	12.0	12.0	12.0
DL - Methionine	g/kg	2.40	2.40	2.40	2.40
L - Lysine	g/kg	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.90
L - Threonine	g/kg	0.30	0.30	0.20	0.30
Tixosil ³	g/kg	6.00	6.00	3.00	-
Maltodextrin	g/kg	23.3	20.2	11.7	-
White grape marc extract	g/kg	-	5.60	21.0	42.0
Calculated nutrient composition					
AME _N ⁴	MJ/kg	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Crude protein	%	22.0	22.0	22.0	22.0
Crude fibre	%	2.35	2.34	2.34	2.33
Crude fat	%	8.11	8.09	7.87	7.66
Crude ash	%	6.41	6.41	6.15	5.88
Lysine	%	1.26	1.26	1.26	1.26
Methionine	%	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57
Tryptophan	%	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26
Threonine	%	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88
Calcium	%	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93
Phosphorus	%	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71
Analyzed nutrient composition					
Dry matter	%	90.2	90.4	90.5	90.4
Crude protein	%	22.5	22.8	22.1	22.1
Crude fiber	%	2.74	2.39	2.59	2.44
Crude fat	%	7.47	7.49	7.56	7.23
Crude ash	%	6.08	6.42	5.92	5.93
Calcium	%	1.03	1.07	1.00	1.02
Phosphorus	%	0.61	0.63	0.61	0.61

¹ CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg

² Contents per kg feed: 7,200 I.U. Vit. A (retinyl-acetate); 1,400 I.U. Vit. D₃; 12 I.U. Vit. E (α - tocopherol acetate); 2.4 mg Vit. K₃ (menadione nicotinamide bisulfite); 3.0 mg Vit. B₁ (mononitrate); 5.04 mg Vit. B₂ (cryst. riboflavin); 3.6 mg Vit. B₆ (pyridoxin - HCl); 18 μg Vit. B₁₂; 36 mg niacin (niacinamide); 150 μg biotin (commercial. feed grade); 1.2 mg folic acid (cryst. commercial. feed grade); 12 mg pantothenic acid (Ca D - pantothenate); 720 mg choline (chloride); 60 mg iron (iron carbonate); 60 mg zinc (zinc sulfate); 72 mg manganese (manganous oxide); 12 mg copper (copper oxide); 0.54 mg iodine (calcium - iodate); 0.24 mg selenium (sodium - selenite); 1.68 g sodium (NaCl); 0.66 g magnesium (magnesium sulfate); carrier: calcium carbonate (calcium min 38 %)

³ Tixosil: silicon dioxide >97 %, Solvay GmbH, Hannover, Germany

⁴ Estimated according to equation of WPSA 1984.

diet from days 11 to 35 (Table 2). Tixosil (silicon dioxide > 97 %, Solvay GmbH, Hannover, Germany) was added as an indigestible substance to allow the inclusion of the extract at the highest concentration without introducing additional nutrients from other ingredients that were modified in the feed formulation. Fifty kg of the grower diet were separated and supplemented with 2 % of Celite 545 (Carl Roth GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) as an inert marker for later determining the apparent ileal digestibility (AID) of nutrients, and administered to the animals the last four days of the trial.

Performance parameters

The average pen BW and feed intake were recorded for the periods from days 0 to 10, 11 to 21, and 22 to 35. Thus, average daily feed intake (ADFI), body weight gain (BWG), and feed conversion ratio (FCR) were calculated for the different periods and for the whole experimental period.

Sampling procedures

On day 35, 30 broiler chickens from each treatment group whose BW

Table 2

Composition of the grower diets for broiler chickens (11 to 35 days) with varying polyphenol levels.

		CON ¹	LPP	MPP	HPP
Ingredient composition					
Maize	g/kg	325	322	319	315
Soybean meal	g/kg	273	273	274	276
Wheat	g/kg	282	283	278	271
Soybean oil	g/kg	55.0	55.0	55.0	55.0
Limestone	g/kg	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Monocalcium - phosphate	g/kg	13.0	13.0	13.0	13.0
Premix ²	g/kg	12.0	12.0	12.0	12.0
DL-Methionine	g/kg	2.30	2.30	2.30	2.30
L - Lysine	g/kg	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60
L - Threonine	g/kg	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Maltodextrin	g/kg	23.3	20.2	11.7	-
White grape marc extract	g/kg	-	5.60	21.0	42.0
Calculated nutrient composition					
AME _N ³	MJ/kg	12.8	12.8	12.8	12.8
Crude protein	%	20.1	20.1	20.0	20.0
Crude fibre	%	2.35	2.35	2.33	2.31
Crude fat	%	7.74	7.73	7.72	7.70
Crude ash	%	5.17	5.18	5.20	5.24
Lysine	%	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16
Methionine	%	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.53
Tryptophan	%	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23
Threonine	%	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79
Calcium	%	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79
Phosphorus	%	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.56
Analyzed composition					
Dry matter	%	89.6	89.6	89.0	90.1
Crude protein	%	21.1	20.7	20.7	19.8
Crude fiber	%	2.22	2.18	2.32	2.22
Crude fat	%	7.23	7.09	6.53	7.05
Crude ash	%	6.73	6.87	6.75	7.03
Calcium	%	0.79	0.81	0.76	0.83
Phosphorus	%	0.60	0.59	0.59	0.59

¹ CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg

² Contents per kg feed: 7,200 I.U. Vit. A (retinyl-acetate); 1,400 I.U. Vit. D₃; 12 I.U. Vit. E (α-tocopherol acetate); 2.4 mg Vit. K₃ (menadione nicotinamide bisulfite); 3.0 mg Vit. B₁ (mononitrate); 5.04 mg Vit. B₂ (cryst. riboflavin); 3.6 mg Vit. B₆ (pyridoxin - HCl); 18 μg Vit. B₁₂; 36 mg niacin (niacinamide); 150 μg biotin (commercial. feed grade); 1.2 mg folic acid (cryst. commercial. feed grade); 12 mg pantothenic acid (Ca D - pantothenate); 720 mg choline (chloride); 60 mg iron (iron carbonate); 60 mg zinc (zinc sulfate); 72 mg manganese (manganous oxide); 12 mg copper (copper oxide); 0.54 mg iodine (calcium - iodate); 0.24 mg selenium (sodium - selenite); 1.68 g sodium (NaCl); 0.66 g magnesium (magnesium sulfate); carrier: calcium carbonate (calcium min 38 %)

³ Estimated according to equation of WPSA 1984.

was closest to the mean of the corresponding treatment group were selected (3 birds per pen), stunned, and euthanized by exsanguination. Ileal digesta from the posterior half between Meckel's diverticulum and 2 cm before the ileo-ceco-colic junction was collected and stored at -20 °C for chemical analysis. They were used for the calculation of the AID of some nutrients using the following formula:

$$AID \% = 100 - \left(\frac{\% \text{ marker in feed}}{\% \text{ marker in ileum}} \times \frac{\% \text{ nutrient in ileum}}{\% \text{ nutrient in feed}} \right) \times 100$$

Another 10 birds from each treatment group (one bird per pen) were selected to collect and preserve jejunum and cecum tissues in formalin for histological analysis. Chicken breasts were harvested, rapidly frozen in liquid nitrogen, and then stored at -80 °C for subsequent lipid oxidation assessment. Additionally, 32 chickens (eight per treatment group, one per pen) were slaughtered, and the jejunum tissues collected for Ussing chamber studies or for determining the gene expression of tight junction proteins, various cytokines, and nutrient transporters.

Histological Procedures

Intestinal tissue was fixed in 4 % phosphate-buffered formaldehyde, dehydrated, and embedded in paraffin. Histo-fixed jejunum and cecum samples were cut into 5 μm sections using a microtome (Type 1400 Fa. Leitz Wetzlar, Germany). After drying in the 37 °C incubator, the tissue on the slide was dewaxed with xylene and rehydrated in graded ethanol. Alcian blue pH 2.5 - periodic acid-Schiff (AB - 8GX, Sigma; Schiff reagents, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) staining procedure was used to stain jejunal and cecal tissues (Liu et al., 2014). All the pictures were examined with a light microscope (Photomicroscope BX43F Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) connected with an attached digital camera (Olympus DP72, Tokyo, Japan).

Villus length (VL) and crypt depth (CD) were measured using the cellSens imaging software (v. 1.4, Olympus). The number and distribution of GC in the jejunal villi and crypts, as well as in the cecal crypts, were calculated using QuPath software (v. 0.4.3). Ten crypts and villi per section were measured for each animal. VL was defined as the distance from the crypt opening to the top of the villus, while CD was defined as the distance from the crypt base to the crypt mouth (Schregel et al., 2022). The villus-to-crypt ratio (V/C) was calculated as the ratio of VL to CD. Additionally, the ratio of GC count to corresponding area (expressed as × 10³ cells per square millimeter) was determined separately for crypts and villi.

Gene expression

The jejunum tissue was cut into small pieces, and 15 mg ± 1.5 mg of each treatment group was used for RNA extraction. Total RNA was extracted using NucleoSpin RNA Plus kit (Macherey-Nagel GmbH and Company KG, Düren, Germany) following the manufacturer's instructions. The extracted RNA was then purified using the RNase-Free DNase Set kit (Qiagen, Hamburg, Germany, 79254). The quality of the RNA was assessed using the Bioanalyzer 2100 and the RNA 6000 Nano kit (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany).

The SuperScript III Reverse Transcriptase kit (Agilent Technologies) was used to reverse-transcribe 500 ng of the purified RNA into cDNA in a SureCycler 8800 (Agilent Technologies). The expression levels of the following genes were analyzed: tumor necrosis factor alpha, claudin 5, interleukin 8 (IL-8), mucin 2, and zonula occludens 1. For data normalization, β-actin, glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, and β2-microglobulin were used as housekeeping genes (Suppl. Table 2).

To account for differences in mRNA abundance between targets, either a 1/25 or 1/50 dilution was used for quantification (Schregel et al., 2022). Real-time fluorescence quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) detection was performed using the AriaMax Real-Time PCR System (Agilent Technologies). Melting curves and PCR efficiency

were employed as standard quality criteria for each RT-qPCR run (Liu et al., 2014).

Determination of lipid oxidation

The fluorometric measurement was conducted according to the manufacturer's instructions for the commercially available lipid peroxidation (MDA) assay kit (Sigma-Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany), with the following modification: Malonaldehyde bis(dimethylacetal) (MDA) was used as the standard (Aguilar Diaz De Leon and Borges, 2020). A 0.550 mM stock solution was prepared by diluting 9.2 μL of MDA (Fisher Scientific, Schwerte, Germany) in 100 mL of H_2O , stirring for 10 min. This stock solution was further diluted to 0.2 mM and 0.02 mM to prepare standard solutions ranging from 0.2 μM to 6 μM MDA. The 2-thiobarbituric acid (TBA; Sigma-Aldrich) was dissolved in 30 % acetic acid according to the manufacturer's instructions. Fluorometric measurements were performed using the Infinite MPlux plate reader (Tecan Group Ltd., Männedorf, Switzerland) at excitation wavelength $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 515$ nm and emission wavelength $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 553$ nm, with black 96-well microtiter plates (Greiner Bio-One, Frickenhausen, Germany).

Ussing chamber studies

For the electrophysiological measurements, eight broilers per treatment group were used, with tissues from each animal mounted in three chambers. After euthanasia, the abdominal cavity was opened, and the jejunum was carefully removed and immediately placed in oxygenated, ice-cold modified Krebs-Henseleit buffer containing glucose (10 mM glucose, 2 mM mannitol, 115 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 25 mM NaHCO_3 , 0.6 mM NaH_2PO_4 , 2.4 mM Na_2HPO_4 , 1.2 mM MgCl_2 , 1.5 mM CaCl_2 , pH 7.4). The muscle layer of the jejunum was removed with a glass slide, and the mucosal tissue was mounted in the Ussing chamber with an exposed area of 0.79 cm^2 . Krebs-Henseleit buffer without glucose was added to each chamber, under continuous oxygenation at 38 °C to maintain tissue vitality. After mounting the tissue, electrical measurements were conducted by assessing the transepithelial potential difference using a microcomputer-controlled voltage/current clamp (K. Mussler Scientific Instruments, Aachen, Deutschland). In addition, tissue conductance (Gt) was measured to assess the condition of the tissue. Tissue conductance corresponds to the reciprocal of tissue resistance and is expressed in milli Siemens per square centimeter ($\text{mS}\cdot\text{cm}^2$). Following an equilibration period of approximately 20–30 min, the tissues were short-circuited by setting the voltage to 0 mV. To assess the absorption capacity, glucose (10 mM) was initially added to the mucosal side of the epithelium, whereas mannitol was simultaneously added to the serosal side to maintain osmotic balance. After that and reaching a stable baseline, lysine (10 mM) was applied to the mucosal side, as an additional substrate for absorption test, with mannitol again used on the serosal side to ensure osmotic equilibrium. At the end of the collection period, carbachol solution (0.1 mM) was added to the basolateral compartment to stimulate chloride ion secretion. To represent the electrogenic transport processes, changes in the short-circuit current (ΔIsc) and tissue conductance (ΔGt) were calculated by determining the difference between the average values during the last three minutes before and after each substance application.

Chemical analyses

Chemical analyses of feed samples included Weende constituents and, additionally, amino acids (AA), calcium (Ca), and phosphorus (P). Analyses were conducted in accordance with the methods issued by the Association of German Agricultural Analytic and Research Institutes (VDLUFA): dry matter: VDLUFA III 3.1; crude protein (CP): VDLUFA III 4.1.2 modified according to macro-N determination (vario MAX CN); AA: VDLUFA III 4.11.1; crude fiber: VDLUFA III 6.1.4; crude ash: VDLUFA III 8.1; crude fat: VDLUFA III 5.1.1; starch: VDLUFA III 7.2.1;

Ca, P, and sodium: VDLUFA VII 2.2.2.6. Pooled ileal samples were ground to pass through a 0.25 mm screen and analyzed for CP, crude ash, Ca, P, and AA. Celite was measured in feed and ileal digesta according to the method VDLUFA III 8.2.

The GME was analyzed in terms of TPC by the Folin-Ciocalteu methodology, adapted from Rubio et al. (2022) guidelines, by using 96-well plates and a microplate reader (BMG LABTECH, Ortenberg, Germany). The quantification of individual polyphenols in the GME was performed by LC-MS/MS using a Thermo Scientific (San Jose, CA, USA) TSQ Quantum Ultra™ triple quadrupole mass spectrometer with a heated electrospray ionization (HESI) source. The separation and identification conditions were previously optimized by Celeiro et al. (2021). Selected reaction monitoring (SRM) working mode, scanning simultaneously in both negative and positive modes and monitoring two or three MS/MS transitions for each compound was selected for an unequivocal identification and quantification of the polyphenols. External calibration (standard solutions between 0.01 to 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was used for the quantification of polyphenols.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics software, Version 29 (IBM, Chicago, Illinois, USA). All data, with the exception of the gene expression, were evaluated using ANOVA followed by the post-hoc Tukey's test when data were normally distributed. With non-normally distributed data, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used. Data are presented as means with standard error of the mean. Statistical significance was determined at $P < 0.05$. Gene expression was analyzed using the REST 2009 software (Pfaffl et al., 2002). Differences between treatment groups for each gene of interest were evaluated, with statistical significance set at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Growth performance of broiler chickens

During the first days of the trial, some animals exhibited anorexia and, additionally, spraddled legs were observed in a relatively high number of animals. Some birds had to be culled in compliance with animal welfare rules. For the remainder of the trial, most animals maintained good health status. However, possibly due to their good performance and, in some cases, very high BW, a considerable number of animals again developed spraddled legs and had to be culled. The combined mortality and culling rates accounted for 5 %. Table 3 shows the results for growth performance during the starter period, grower period, and overall cycle. No significant differences ($P > 0.05$) were observed in initial and final BW, BWG, ADFI, and FCR among the four treatment groups.

Apparent ileal digestibility of nutrients

The effects of different concentrations of the GME on AID of 35-day-old broiler chickens are shown in Table 4. The addition of the GME had no effect on AID of most nutrients ($P > 0.05$). However, AID of aspartic acid increased with the level of polyphenols in the three treatment groups. Accordingly, MPP and HPP showed higher AID of aspartic acid (80.6 % and 80.9 %, respectively) than LPP (76.3 %) ($P = 0.006$), while differences with the control group were not significant.

Intestinal morphology

Histomorphological findings and images of the measured areas are presented in Table 5 and Suppl. Fig. 1, respectively. No significant differences were found for VL, CD, or V/C in the jejunum, or for CD in the cecum among treatment groups.

The number of GC in the jejunum and cecum of broiler chickens was

Table 3
Growth performance of broiler chickens receiving the solid white grape marc extract at different concentrations.

	CON ¹	LPP	MPP	HPP	SEM ²	P-value
Starter period (1-10 days of age)						
Initial body weight (g)	36.9	36.9	36.8	36.6	0.14	0.870
Final body weight (g)	184	187	192	186	2.45	0.678
Body weight gain (g)	147	150	156	154	2.22	0.568
Daily feed intake (g/day)	24.1	22.9	25.4	25.4	0.46	0.197
Feed conversion ratio	1.57	1.46	1.50	1.59	0.03	0.390
Grower period (11-35 days of age)						
Initial body weight (g)	184	187	192	186	2.45	0.678
Final body weight (g)	2,134	2,056	2,113	2,164	18.8	0.260
Body weight gain (g)	1,950	1,871	1,921	1,978	17.5	0.194
Daily feed intake (g/day)	107	107	108	112	1.12	0.263
Feed conversion ratio	1.37	1.39	1.41	1.42	0.01	0.121
Overall period (1-35 days of age)						
Initial body weight (g)	36.9	36.9	36.8	36.6	0.14	0.870
Final body weight (g)	2,134	2,056	2,113	2,164	18.8	0.260
Body weight gain (g)	2,097	2,019	2,076	2,125	18.9	0.278
Daily feed intake (g/day)	83.3	83.1	84.7	87.6	0.82	0.188
Feed conversion ratio	1.39	1.41	1.43	1.44	0.01	0.083

¹ CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg

² Standard error of the mean

Table 4
Apparent nutrient ileal digestibility (%) in 35-day-old broiler chickens receiving the solid white grape marc extract at different concentrations.

	CON ¹	LPP	MPP	HPP	SEM ²	P-value
Crude protein	80.4	80.7	81.8	79.4	0.45	0.290
Calcium	41.3	42.7	39.2	45.5	0.99	0.149
Phosphorus	56.4	56.2	56.4	57.4	0.70	0.794
Magnesium	28.1	24.3	23.9	25.9	1.32	0.665
Potassium	90.9	91.7	90.7	92.0	0.27	0.273
Crude fat	96.1	95.2	95.7	95.7	0.49	0.946
Lysine	83.6	84.0	85.9	84.7	0.43	0.272
Methionine	86.0	87.1	86.2	88.5	0.55	0.350
Cystine	73.3	74.6	74.4	72.5	0.58	0.528
Threonine	74.9	75.0	77.8	76.3	0.58	0.237
Aspartic acid	77.6 ^{ab}	76.3 ^b	80.6 ^a	80.9 ^a	0.58	0.006
Serine	79.1	78.9	82.2	80.3	0.53	0.086
Glutamic acid	87.1	86.4	88.4	86.4	0.38	0.136
Glycine	77.0	76.9	79.9	78.5	0.53	0.148
Alanine	78.0	78.4	80.5	79.7	0.55	0.350
Valine	75.1	77.3	78.1	77.0	0.60	0.366
Isoleucine	79.3	81.3	82.1	81.3	0.55	0.301
Leucine	81.4	81.2	83.6	82.4	0.51	0.316
Tyrosine	81.7	80.6	83.7	82.9	0.51	0.158
Phenylalanine	82.9	82.7	84.8	82.9	0.45	0.286
Histidine	81.7	81.7	84.2	82.3	0.43	0.107
Arginine	86.8	86.6	88.9	88.0	0.35	0.068
Proline	83.0	82.6	84.1	80.8	0.47	0.075
Total amino acids	81.7	81.7	83.8	82.4	0.44	0.304

¹ CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg

² Standard error of the mean

^{a,b,c} Means with different superscripts within the same row differ significantly

significantly affected by the addition of the GME. In the jejunum, the 750 mg/kg and 1,500 mg/kg treatment groups showed significantly higher GC counts in both villi and crypts compared to the CON group ($P < 0.001$). However, no significant differences were observed in GC counts in the cecal crypts.

mRNA expression of immune and barrier-related genes in jejunum tissue

The dietary supplementation of different concentrations of the GME extract had no significant effect on the relative expression of genes related to immune response and barrier function in the jejunum

Table 5
Morphology of jejunum and cecum epithelium and goblet cell count in 35-day-old broiler chickens receiving the solid white grape marc extract at different concentrations.

		CON ¹	LPP	MPP	HPP	SEM ²	P-value
Jejunum							
Villus length	μm	1,636	1,689	1,650	1,711	24.6	0.704
Crypt depth	μm	234	231	213	242	6.00	0.371
Villus length / crypt depth		7.14	7.46	8.03	7.16	0.20	0.377
Villus goblet cells	$\times 10^3 / \text{mm}^2$	0.80 ^b	0.96 ^{ab}	1.20 ^a	1.19 ^a	0.04	<0.001
Crypt goblet cells	$\times 10^3 / \text{mm}^2$	2.40 ^c	2.85 ^{bc}	4.03 ^a	3.40 ^{ab}	0.13	<0.001
Cecum							
Crypt depth	μm	335	339	348	338	5.65	0.867
Crypt goblet cells	$\times 10^3 / \text{mm}^2$	0.57	0.76	0.74	0.58	0.04	0.153

¹ CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg

² Standard error of the mean

(Table 6).

Antioxidant capacity

The addition of different concentrations of the GME did not show differences in lipid peroxidation in the breast muscle of 35-day-old broiler chickens, as indicated by the MDA assay results (Fig. 1).

Ussing chamber measurements

Upon the addition of glucose to the jejunum, Isc increased in all treatments (Table 7). Although there was no significant difference between treatments ($P = 0.154$), the HPP group showed the highest numerical increase. Addition of lysine resulted in a slight increase in Isc in all treatments. Once again, even though the HPP group recorded a numerically higher Isc, the differences between the groups were not statistically significant ($P = 0.827$). Carbachol caused an increase in Isc across all treatments, and, again, the difference between treatments was not statistically significant ($P = 0.162$), although HPP registered the numerically highest increase. The addition of glucose registered a decrease in Gt in all the groups receiving the GME ($P = 0.002$). Lysine- and carbachol-induced changes in Gt were not significantly different between treatments ($P = 0.191$ and $P = 0.623$, respectively).

Discussion

This study investigated the effects of dietary supplementation with a solid white GME, a by-product rich in bioactive polyphenolic compounds, on growth performance, nutrient digestibility, gut morphology, antioxidant capacity, intestinal barrier function, and nutrient transport in broiler chickens. The results, while largely non-significant in terms of growth metrics, provide important insights into how polyphenol-rich feed additives may influence specific physiological aspects, particularly gut health and immune modulation. The exploration of natural polyphenols as alternatives to antibiotics in animal feed has gained significant traction over recent years (Lipiński et al., 2017). This shift is driven by the need to minimize the negative impacts of antibiotic use in livestock, including harmful side effects and the accumulation of drug residues and antimicrobial resistance genes in animal products (Hassan et al., 2019). Among the potential natural alternatives, grape-derived

Table 6

Relative expression ratio of some genes related to immune response and barrier function in the jejunum of 35-day-old broiler chickens receiving the solid white grape marc extract at different concentrations (analyzed with REST 2009).

	CON ¹ vs. LPP		CON vs. MPP		CON vs. HPP		LPP vs. MPP		LPP vs. HPP		MPP vs. HPP	
	Ratio	P-value	Ratio	P-value	Ratio	P-value	Ratio	P-value	Ratio	P-value	Ratio	P-value
TNF-α	1.52	0.092	1.05	0.856	1.09	0.735	0.69	0.078	0.72	0.136	0.69	0.066
Claudin 5	1.15	0.339	1.05	0.652	0.89	0.262	0.92	0.586	0.78	0.100	0.92	0.605
IL-8	0.89	0.797	0.67	0.388	0.71	0.415	0.75	0.494	0.80	0.491	0.75	0.521
Mucin 2	0.92	0.677	1.22	0.390	0.91	0.680	1.34	0.094	0.99	0.943	1.34	0.121
ZO-1	1.05	0.691	1.01	0.970	0.96	0.754	0.96	0.681	0.91	0.525	0.96	0.696

¹ CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg; TNF-α: tumor necrosis factor alpha, IL-8: interleukin-8, ZO-1: zonula occludens 1

Fig. 1. Malondialdehyde concentrations in breast muscle of 35-day-old broiler chickens receiving the solid white grape marc extract at different concentrations. MDA = Malondialdehyde; CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg. Results are shown in means ± standard error.

Table 7

Change in short-circuit current (I_{sc}) and tissue conductance (Gt) after glucose, lysine and carbachol addition in Ussing chambers in jejunum tissues of 35-day-old broiler chickens receiving the solid white grape marc extract at different concentrations.

	CON ¹	LPP	MPP	HPP	SEM ²	P-value ³
$ \Delta I_{sc} ^4$ ($\mu A/cm^2$)						
Glucose	5.81	4.39	3.94	10.1	0.952	0.154
Lysine	0.80	0.63	0.60	1.82	0.235	0.827
Carbachol	1.88	1.46	2.18	3.79	0.341	0.162
$ \Delta G_t $ (mS/cm ²)						
Glucose	0.21 ^a	0.10 ^b	0.06 ^b	0.09 ^b	0.017	0.002
Lysine	0.28	0.14	0.13	0.16	0.028	0.191
Carbachol	0.67	0.28	0.24	0.41	0.096	0.623

¹ CON = control group; LPP = 200 mg/kg feed of polyphenols; MPP = 750 mg/kg; HPP = 1,500 mg/kg

² Standard error of the mean

³ Statistical comparisons were performed using Kruskal-Wallis (I_{sc} : Carbachol, Gt: Glucose and Carbachol) and ANOVA (I_{sc} : Glucose and Lysine, Gt Glucose) test

⁴ $|\Delta I_{sc}|$ = change of short-circuit current; $|\Delta G_t|$ = change of tissue conductance
^{a,b,c} Means with different superscripts within the same row differ significantly

polyphenols have emerged as a promising option (Mahfuz et al., 2021).

In recent years, numerous studies have explored the potential benefits of using grape by-products as feed additives in animal nutrition. However, the variety of products used makes it difficult to draw clear

conclusions and to compare results across studies. For instance, by-products such as grape marc and grape pomace, solid residues from winemaking, have been tested as raw materials, but their characteristics are not clearly defined (Muhlack et al., 2018; Antonic et al., 2020). Additionally, various methods for extracting and concentrating bioactive compounds from these materials have been employed, resulting in a range of extracts with significantly different polyphenolic profiles (Coelho et al., 2020; Pagano et al., 2021). It is also important to note that the grape variety from which the by-products originate can also lead to substantial differences in composition. These significant variations in composition also make it challenging to determine the optimal amount to use in feed.

In this study, the grape marc was obtained from Albariño white grapes, a variety used in the production of white wine from the region of Galicia (Rías Baixas appellation of origin, NW Spain). The organic solvent for extraction of bioactive compounds was completely volatilized to obtain an aqueous liquid extract that was later spray-dried to obtain a solid extract using maltodextrin as carrier. As commented above, due to differences in the products used in previous studies and the complex polyphenolic composition of the extract tested, appropriate dosing could not rely solely on existing evidence. The literature shows significant discrepancies in the minimum effective concentrations of polyphenol-rich extracts: some studies report effects at low concentrations (even below 50 ppm) under normal or stress conditions (Yang et al., 2017; He et al., 2019; Mohebodini et al., 2019; Ao and Kim, 2020), while others observed limited effects even at higher doses than those used in this study (Payá et al., 2010; Chamorro et al., 2013; Chamorro et al., 2019; Huerta et al., 2022). Therefore, this study selected practical and cost-effective concentrations, avoiding excessively high doses.

The potential benefits of grape by-products on broiler growth performance have been investigated in recent years, but results remain inconsistent. In this study, the TPC of the GME was 35 g/kg, and diets were supplemented to achieve three polyphenol concentrations: 200, 750, and 1,500 mg/kg of feed. None of these levels significantly affected growth performance. These findings align with previous studies using various winemaking by-products (Mavrommatis et al., 2021; Erinle et al., 2022; Huerta et al., 2022).

Other studies on the use of grape by-products in broiler chickens reported impaired growth performance, although this effect was dependent on the dosage or the type of ingredient. For example, the addition of untreated grape pomace resulted in lower BW in 42-day-old broilers, but this negative effect was mitigated by pre-treating the pomace with polyethylene glycol (Kumanda et al., 2019). Additionally, the inclusion of 6 % grape skin reduced the daily weight gain of 21-day-old broilers, whereas a 3 % inclusion showed no significant differences with no differences observed between fermented and unfermented material (Nardoia et al., 2020). Moreover, the use of three different concentrations of grape seeds (1 %, 2 %, and 4 %) showed an improvement in BWG with the low and medium concentrations. The 2 % concentration resulted in a better FCR, whereas the highest concentration (4 %) negatively impacted performance parameters (Abu Hafsa and Ibrahim, 2018).

In the current study, supplementation with GME appeared to increase the FCR, which may have a negative economic impact. However, as previously mentioned, the results reported in the literature are inconsistent (Costa et al. 2022), and additional studies are required to confirm the validity of this effect.

In summary, the inconsistency in the results shown by the previous studies can be attributable to many factors such as variations in the type of raw material (grape skin, grape pomace, grape seed extract, etc.), the application of pre-treatments, the concentration of polyphenols or other experimental conditions.

There is a paucity of research on the effects of grape extracts on nutrient AID, particularly in poultry. The effects of the GME on AID of several nutrients were very limited in the current study. Few studies have measured the AID following the use of dietary grape products in broilers, and the variation in the tested products further complicates comparisons. The use of a grape seed extract in 21-day-old chickens also showed a limited effect on AID of CP and AA but it seemed that very high concentrations of polyphenols (5,000 mg/kg) were detrimental (Chamorro et al., 2013). A decrease in ileal protein digestibility was observed in a study using 6 % of unfermented grape skin (Nardoia et al., 2020). The same study registered numerically lower digestibility with 6 % of fermented grape skin and 3 % of fermented or unfermented grape skin, but differences were not significant. However, this kind of product is rich in fibers which could have been responsible for the decrease in digestibility. On the contrary, the use of grape pomace as ingredient in broiler chickens' diets seems to have no effect on nutrient AID according to several studies (Goñi et al., 2007; Aditya et al., 2018) or very limited (Lichovnikova et al., 2015) despite its dietary fiber content.

Regarding the influence of the GME on gut barrier function, the current study found no effect on the measured gene expressions. These findings contrast with those of Cao et al. (2020), who observed that the inclusion of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg of a grape seed extract seemed to reduce the expression of IL-8 in jejunal mucosa, while the highest concentration seemed to decrease IL-6 expression in the ileal mucosa of broilers.

Previous studies have indicated that the responsiveness of intestinal barrier-related genes to dietary interventions may vary depending on the intestinal segment being studied. For instance, the ileum may be more responsive to polyphenol supplementation than the jejunum (Barekatin et al., 2021). Additionally, the expression of genes related to gut health and inflammation can vary across different stages of broiler growth (Barekatin et al., 2019). In the current study, we only assessed gene expression at day 35, which may have limited the ability to detect changes that occur earlier in the development. Future studies should consider examining multiple time points and intestinal segments to capture the full spectrum of polyphenol effects on gene expression.

Oxidative stress is a major challenge in poultry production, as it can lead to the excessive generation of reactive oxygen species, which damage cellular structures and impair growth performance. Grape by-products are rich in phenolic compounds with potential antioxidant capacity (Mattos et al., 2017). One of the key markers of oxidative stress is MDA, a product of lipid peroxidation (Del Rio et al., 2005). In this study, we measured the MDA content in broiler breast muscle and found no significant differences between the control and the groups receiving the GME. A recent study showed that the use of low levels of grape seed extract (100 mg/kg) in broiler chickens were able to revert the negative effects of the use of oxidized rice bran oil, which was observed by measuring several markers of liver dysfunction as well as MDA in serum and liver (Wang et al., 2024). In fact, the use of low concentrations of polyphenol concentrates derived from grapes and onions can be effective in reducing oxidative damage under adverse conditions, such as the presence of mycotoxins, although the effect was limited in the case of heating stress (Mazur-Kušnerek et al., 2019a; Mazur-Kušnerek et al., 2019b).

A previous study investigating fermented and unfermented grape skin reported antioxidant effects only at the highest inclusion levels of

both products, corresponding to 2,270 mg/kg and 3,130 mg/kg of polyphenols. These effects were comparable to those observed with vitamin E supplementation (Nardoia et al., 2020). In fact, unfermented grape products possess lower polyphenol concentration. This suggests that higher concentrations of polyphenols may be required to observe significant antioxidant effects in broilers not subjected to stressors. In this line, another study found that 5,000 mg/kg of tannic acid or the same concentration of gallic acid supplemented in feed of broiler chickens were effective in decreasing lipid oxidation in breast muscle (Starčević et al., 2015).

The morphological integrity of the intestine is a critical factor in nutrient absorption and overall gut health. Intestinal villi are the part of the mucosa responsible for absorption while crypts are related with cell turnover. Longer villi indicate a larger absorptive area, while deeper crypts may suggest enhanced cell renewal to compensate for the loss of epithelial cells from the villi. Moreover, there is an association between gut morphology and performance in broiler chickens (Rysman et al., 2023).

The supplementation with a white GME accounting for 200, 750, and 1,500 mg/kg of polyphenols did not result in significant changes in jejunum or cecum epithelial morphology in the current study. These findings align with those of a previous study, which found no significant effects on cecum morphology in broilers fed a diet supplemented with white grape extract at concentrations of 165 mg/kg and 585 mg/kg of procyanidins and other polyphenols, respectively (Duangnumswang et al., 2022). In another study the dietary inclusion of 2.5 or 5.0 g/kg of a powdered polyphenol-rich grape extract did not affect jejunal morphology in 21-day-old broiler chickens (Chamorro et al., 2019). On the contrary, a recent study reported an improvement in gut morphology of different intestinal segments with polyphenol-rich phytochemical feed additives, one of them being freeze-dried grape pomace, under both, thermoneutral and heat stress conditions, although information about the polyphenol concentration was not provided (Oretomiloye and Adewole, 2024). In this line, the use of 300 and 600 mg/kg of epigallocatechin-3-gallate in 2-week-old broiler chickens showed a clear improvement of jejunal morphology of 21-, 28- and 35-day-old chickens subjected to heat stress (Song et al., 2019). Furthermore, supplementing broiler feed with 7.5, 15, or 30 mg/kg of proanthocyanidins, polyphenolic compounds found in grape seeds, resulted in a noticeable effect in jejunal morphology in 21- and 42-day-old chickens, as evidenced by an increased V/C (Yang et al., 2017).

An important measurement related with barrier function integrity is the GC count. GC are responsible for producing mucus, which plays a crucial role in protecting the intestinal epithelium and facilitating nutrient absorption (Duangnumswang et al., 2021).

Our study did reveal a significant increase in the number of GC in jejunal villi and crypts with the medium and highest concentrations of polyphenols. The increased GC count observed in this study suggests that the GME may enhance gut health by supporting mucus production (Lu et al., 2021).

Most published studies have been conducted in models other than broilers, such as swine or, more commonly, mice for *in vivo* experiments, as well as various *in vitro* cell lines. Many of these studies have focused on individual polyphenols, although some have examined more complex extracts, a few of which are comparable to the one tested in the present study. Among polyphenols, resveratrol is the most extensively studied and has demonstrated a range of effects on intestinal barrier function (Sandoval-Ramírez et al., 2021).

There are scarce data on the effect of grape polyphenols in intestinal GC count of healthy broiler chickens. The dietary inclusion of 2,500 or 5,000 mg/kg of a grape extract in 21-day-old broiler chickens had no effect on the jejunal GC number (Chamorro et al., 2019). However, the highest dose led to a decrease in sialic acid but had no effect on the total mucin content in ileal digesta compared to the control group.

In line with our results but testing the effects of polyphenols from a different source, a study using 1,000, 2,000 and 3,000 mg/kg of a

phenolic-rich onion extract in broiler chickens up to 35 days of age observed also an increase in GC count in duodenum, jejunum and ileum with the two highest doses (Omar et al., 2020). Under heat stress conditions, resveratrol, a natural polyphenol, seems to have a protective effect on intestinal epithelium by increasing the number of GC (Liu et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2021). Interestingly, Yang et al. (2021) also observed an increase in jejunal GC count in animals not exposed to a stressor. However, clear conclusions about how polyphenols affect barrier integrity are still lacking and require more research to understand the molecular mechanisms involved.

The Ussing chamber technique is a well-established tool that allows to assess nutrient transport and intestinal barrier function through electrophysiological measurements. Thus, Isc is an indicator of active ion transport (Boudry, 2005), while Gt is an indicator of epithelial permeability and, therefore, epithelial barrier function (Karaki, 2023). In this study, we used the Ussing chamber technique to evaluate the effects of the GME on glucose and lysine transport in the jejunum of 35-day-old broilers. The results of the current study suggest an increased response, as measured by Isc, following the addition of glucose, lysine, and carbachol in the HPP group, which could indicate enhanced epithelial transport. However, no significant differences were observed, likely due to high variability within the groups. On the other hand, the results also suggest that dietary GME may have a slight effect in decreasing Gt, which could reflect reduced paracellular permeability in these groups and, consequently, a stronger barrier function. To date, there have been only a few studies utilizing the Ussing chamber to explore the effects of polyphenols as feed additives on the physiological state of the small intestine in broiler chickens, although some *in vitro* studies have been conducted on pig tissues. The addition of phenolic compounds in the Ussing chamber, rather than as feed additives as done in the current study, complicates the comparison between these studies.

According to previous reports, experiments on pig jejunum and ileum tissues showed that the Isc induced by glucose was significantly reduced after the addition of some polyphenols, such as trans-resveratrol and ϵ -viniferin. This indicates that polyphenols can inhibit glucose absorption in the jejunum and ileum of pigs *in vitro* (Guschlbauer et al., 2013; Klinger and Breves, 2018). Possible species-specific differences in polyphenol metabolism may be responsible in part of the opposite trend observed in the current study. However, a limited impact of the polyphenols supplemented in feed cannot be dismissed. Additionally, the jejunum may not be as responsive to polyphenol supplementation as the ileum, as suggested by previous research (Guschlbauer et al., 2013). Although the reduction in Gt may reflect improved barrier function, gene expression data for tight junction and inflammatory markers do not support this finding. This discrepancy may be attributed to regulatory processes at the posttranscriptional or protein level, differences in protein localization that may influence function without altering gene expression, or other mechanisms not assessed in this study (Turner, 2009; Suzuki, 2013). In addition, the lack of stress conditions may have limited the gene-level response to GME (Serafini et al., 2010). Future studies incorporating stress models, time-course sampling, and protein-level analyses are warranted to clarify the mechanisms involved.

In summary, several factors may explain the lack of significant effects on growth performance, nutrient digestibility, and oxidative status observed in this study. First, the concentrations of polyphenols used may not have been sufficient to elicit measurable physiological responses under the tested conditions, particularly in animals not exposed to environmental or metabolic stress, where polyphenols have been shown to be effective additives (Zhu et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2024; Laghari et al., 2025). Second, the bioavailability of polyphenols is a key factor; limited absorption and extensive metabolism within the gastrointestinal tract may reduce their functional efficacy (Abd El-Hack et al., 2023). Finally, the relatively high variability within the treatment groups should not be overlooked.

Despite these limitations, GME was well tolerated and seemed to not negatively affect the performance (with the possible exception of a

potential negative impact on FCR) or health of the birds, suggesting that it may be a safe feed additive with potential for use in various dietary strategies or production scenarios.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the supplementation of a solid white GME at varying concentrations in broiler diets had only minor effects on broiler performance and gut physiology. The lack of effects on performance and gene expression in intestinal tissues at the tested concentrations highlights the need for further investigation into the mechanisms and optimal dosages of polyphenol-rich extracts in poultry feed. Furthermore, none of the tested concentrations resulted in clear adverse effects, although a potential slight negative impact on FCR cannot be ruled out. Future studies should focus on varying the concentrations and patterns of polyphenols and exploring the impact across different stages of broiler development and intestinal segments to fully elucidate their potential in improving poultry gut health and nutrient absorption.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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